

ISic1077

I.Sicily inscription 1077

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

decree

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Phintias

Place of origin (modern)

Licata

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Licata

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140559

1. ἐπὶ ἱεραπό [λου τοῦ δεῖνος]
2. τοῦ Φιλοδά[μου],
3. κατενιαυ [σίου]
4. Φιλοκράτ [εος τοῦ]
5. Ἄριστω [ν— — —]
6. βουλᾶς [άλιασμα κτλ.]
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492705

EDCS 39102234

PHI 140559

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

At 14.0257 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5476

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